

PERINATAL OUTCOMES AND PREDICTORS OF MORTALITY IN SINGLETON BREECH DELIVERIES AT A NIGERIAN REFERRAL CENTER: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY FROM SOUTHERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Breech presentation remains a major contributor to perinatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in low-resource settings. This study assessed perinatal outcomes and predictors of mortality in singleton breech deliveries at a tertiary referral hospital in southern Nigeria. A retrospective review of 209 singleton breech births from January 2008 to December 2012 was conducted using labour, theatre, and neonatal records. Data on maternal booking status, mode of delivery, birth weight, and Apgar scores were analyzed using descriptive and bivariate statistics (χ^2 and Fisher's exact tests), with significance set at $p < 0.05$. The overall perinatal mortality rate was 301.4 per 1,000 births, significantly higher among unbooked mothers (544.3/1,000) than booked (153.9/1,000). Unbooked status strongly predicted intrauterine fetal death on admission (odds ratio = 7.35; 95% CI = 3.13–16.67). Low birth weight (<2.5 kg), Apgar score ≤ 6 , and non-elective delivery modes were significantly associated with poor outcomes. Birth asphyxia was the leading cause of perinatal death. Strengthening antenatal care coverage, improving delivery preparedness, and ensuring skilled management of breech presentations are essential to reduce preventable perinatal deaths in similar settings.

Keywords: Breech delivery, perinatal mortality, Apgar score, low birth weight, Nigeria

Received: 11th February, 2025

Accepted: 28th June, 2025

Published: 30th June, 2025

INTRODUCTION

Breech presentation, defined as a fetal longitudinal lie in which the buttocks or feet present first, remains a significant obstetric challenge and a major determinant of adverse perinatal outcomes. Globally, breech presentation occurs in 3–4% of all term deliveries, with its frequency influenced by parity, gestational age, fetal anomalies, uterine malformations, and placental location (Gray and Shanahan, 2022). In sub-Saharan Africa, where health system limitations constrain timely access to skilled care, breech births contribute disproportionately to fetal morbidity and mortality (Minani and Ross, 2023; Wariri *et al.*, 2025). Despite progress in intrapartum care, breech delivery continues to pose major risks that demand institutional readiness and skilled clinical decision-making.

Perinatal mortality, comprising stillbirths and early neonatal deaths, reflects the effectiveness of obstetric and neonatal care services. In Nigeria, the perinatal

mortality rate (PNMR) was estimated at 39 per 1,000 total births in the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, far above global averages (The Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2019). Breech deliveries, particularly among unbooked or poorly supervised pregnancies, remain major contributors to this burden. Institutional studies in Nigeria have reported PNMRs ranging from 100 to over 500 per 1,000 births, particularly when vaginal breech delivery is attempted without appropriate case selection or skilled attendance (Isah *et al.*, 2022; Kahansim *et al.*, 2016; Shafaatu *et al.*, 2024). These figures reflect systemic challenges such as delayed referral, inadequate monitoring, and limited neonatal resuscitation capacity.

Common complications associated with breech presentation include birth asphyxia, low Apgar scores, intracranial hemorrhage, cord prolapse, and traumatic delivery (Debero Mere *et al.*, 2017). Low birth weight and prematurity further exacerbate these risks, increasing the likelihood of poor neonatal outcomes

(Gantan and Wiedrich, 2023). Understanding how these clinical variables interact to influence fetal survival is essential for designing effective interventions.

The decision between caesarean section and vaginal breech delivery remains complex in Nigeria. Although elective caesarean section has been shown to reduce perinatal risks in term breech presentations, as demonstrated in the Term Breech Trial (Hannah *et al.*, 2000), barriers such as cost, delayed theatre access, and weak referral systems lead to many emergency or unplanned vaginal breech deliveries. Limited fetal monitoring and neonatal support in these settings often worsen outcomes.

This study therefore assessed perinatal outcomes and identified predictors of mortality among singleton breech deliveries at a tertiary referral hospital in southern Nigeria. Specifically, it examined associations between booking status, mode of delivery, birth weight, Apgar scores, and perinatal mortality, with the goal of providing evidence to guide safer management and policy formulation for breech births in similar low-resource environments.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area: This study was conducted at Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital (ISTH), a tertiary referral and training center located in Edo State, Southern Nigeria. ISTH provides comprehensive maternal and neonatal care services to both urban and rural populations across Edo and neighboring states. The facility is equipped with a labour ward, obstetric theatre, and special care baby unit (SCBU), staffed by experienced multidisciplinary personnel, making it a suitable site for studying perinatal outcomes in high-risk deliveries such as breech presentations.

Study Design: A retrospective observational design was adopted. Delivery records covering a five-year period (January 1, 2008–December 31, 2012) were reviewed to assess fetal outcomes in singleton breech births and to identify clinical and demographic predictors of perinatal mortality.

Study Population: The study population included all women who delivered singleton fetuses in breech presentation at ISTH during the study period. Inclusion

criteria were records with complete documentation of fetal outcomes, including Apgar scores and birth weight. Exclusion criteria were multiple gestations, non-breech presentations, and incomplete records. Of 243 identified breech deliveries, 34 were excluded for missing data, yielding a final sample of 209 cases.

Data Collection and Variables: Data were extracted from labour ward registers, operative theatre records, SCBU admission logs, and maternal case files. Collected variables included maternal booking status, gestational age, mode of delivery, Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, birth weight, and fetal complications such as birth asphyxia, cord prolapse, congenital anomalies, or traumatic delivery. Perinatal mortality was defined as any stillbirth (≥ 28 weeks of gestation) or early neonatal death occurring within the first seven days of life. Birth weight was categorized using World Health Organization criteria: low birth weight (< 2.5 kg), normal weight (2.5–3.9 kg), and macrosomia (≥ 4.0 kg). Gestational age distribution and prematurity rates were also assessed when available.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to summarize categorical variables. Associations between perinatal outcomes and predictor variables were tested using Chi-square (χ^2) or Fisher's exact tests, as appropriate, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Multivariate analysis, such as logistic regression, was not performed.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of ISTH. Informed consent was waived because of the retrospective study design and anonymized data. Institutional permission for record access was obtained, and all information was handled confidentially in accordance with established ethical guidelines.

Limitations: Multivariate analysis, such as logistic regression, was not performed. This limitation is acknowledged, as it restricts the ability to adjust for confounding variables and limits causal inference. The retrospective nature of the study posed risks of incomplete or inaccurate documentation. To minimize this, only cases with clearly recorded outcomes were included, and data were verified across multiple sources, including theatre logs and SCBU registers.

Additionally, the absence of certain variables—such as maternal age, time of delivery, and provider skill level—may have affected the ability to fully assess determinants of perinatal outcomes.

RESULTS

Trend in Singleton Breech Deliveries Over Five Years (Figure 1)

The incidence of singleton breech deliveries at the study centre showed a gradual upward trend over the five-year period. Rates increased from 3.99 % in 2008 to 4.65 % in 2009, declined slightly to 4.39 % in 2010, and then rose to 4.72 % in 2011, peaking at 5.07 % in 2012 (Figure 1).

Association between Booking Status and Perinatal Outcomes (Table 1)

Among the 209 singleton breech deliveries reviewed, unbooked mothers were significantly more likely to present with intrauterine fetal death (IUFD) prior to admission. Thirty of seventy-nine unbooked women (38.0 %) had IUFD compared with 10 of 130 booked women (7.7 %) ($\chi^2 = 28.98$, $p < 0.001$; OR = 7.35, 95 % CI = 3.13–16.67). Of the 23 perinatal deaths recorded, 13 (56.5 %) occurred among unbooked mothers and 10 (43.5 %) among booked mothers; the difference was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 0.43$, $p = 0.51$; OR = 1.75, 95 % CI = 0.08–4.00).

Perinatal Mortality Rates by Booking and Admission Status (Figure 2)

The overall perinatal mortality rate (PNMR) was 301.4 per 1,000 births. PNMR among booked women was markedly lower (153.9/1,000) compared with unbooked women (544.3/1,000). For fetuses alive on admission, PNMR was 136.1/1,000, decreasing further among booked mothers (83.3/1,000) versus unbooked (265.3/1,000).

Apgar Scores at Five Minutes by Mode of Delivery (Table 2)

Low Apgar scores (≤ 6) were most frequent among emergency caesarean sections (28/102; 27.5%) and assisted breech deliveries (10/31; 32.3%), compared with elective caesarean sections (5/55; 9.1%). No Apgar scores were recorded for unassisted vaginal breech deliveries because of a high stillbirth rate. The association between mode of delivery and five-minute Apgar score was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 8.68$, $p = 0.013$).

Perinatal Outcomes by Mode of Delivery (Table 3)

Stillbirths were most prevalent among unassisted vaginal breech deliveries (18 / 19; 94.7 %), followed by assisted breech deliveries (6 / 31; 19.4 %) and emergency caesarean sections (7 / 102; 6.9 %). None occurred after elective caesarean section. Early neonatal deaths were most frequent following emergency caesarean section (7 / 102; 6.9 %), with fewer in elective caesarean (2 / 55; 3.6 %) and assisted breech (1 / 31; 3.2 %). Overall survival beyond seven days was highest after elective caesarean section (53 / 55; 96.4 %) and lowest after unassisted vaginal breech delivery (1 / 19; 5.3 %). The association between mode of delivery and perinatal outcome was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 7.09$, $p = 0.029$).

Fetal Outcomes by Birth Weight (Table 4)

Among neonates weighing < 2.5 kg, only 35 (20.7 %) were admitted alive, compared with 114 (67.5 %) in the 2.5–3.5 kg group and 19 (11.8 %) ≥ 3.6 kg ($\chi^2 = 51.80$, $p < 0.001$). Low Apgar scores (≤ 6) occurred in 25 (58.1 %) of neonates < 2.5 kg, 15 (34.9 %) in those 2.5–3.5 kg, and 2 (4.7 %) in those ≥ 3.6 kg ($\chi^2 = 19.00$, $p < 0.001$). Perinatal mortality showed a strong inverse relationship with birth weight: 17 (73.9 %) deaths occurred among neonates < 2.5 kg, 6 (26.1 %) in the 2.5–3.5 kg group and none in the ≥ 3.6 kg category ($\chi^2 = 21.77$, $p < 0.001$).

Distribution of Fetal Complications (Figure 3)

Birth asphyxia was the most frequent fetal complication, affecting 21 (10.1 %) neonates, followed by early neonatal death (12; 5.7 %), neonatal sepsis (10; 4.8 %), jaundice (4; 1.9 %), and arrest of the aftercoming head or congenital anomalies (2 each; 1.0 %).

Clinical Causes of Perinatal Death by Booking Status (Figure 4)

Among the 23 perinatal deaths, birth asphyxia accounted for 10 (43.5 %) cases [4 mothers were booked (40.0 %) and 6 were unbooked (60.0%)]. Antepartum haemorrhage caused 3 (13.0 %) deaths (1 booked, 2 unbooked). Congenital anomalies and neonatal sepsis each contributed 2 (8.7 %) deaths, all among unbooked mothers. The cause of death was undocumented in 6 (26.1 %) cases (5 booked, 1 unbooked).

Table 1: Association between maternal booking status and perinatal outcomes among singleton breech deliveries (n = 209)

Outcome	Booked (n = 130)	Unbooked (n = 79)	OR (95 % CI)	χ^2	p-value
Admission status			7.35 (3.13–16.67)	$\chi^2 = 28.98$	p < 0.001
IUFD prior to admission	10 (7.7 %)	30 (38.0 %)			
Alive on admission	120 (92.3 %)	49 (62.0 %)			
Perinatal mortality (n = 23)			1.75 (0.08–4.00)	0.43	0.51
Fresh stillbirths	4 (36.4 %)	7 (63.6 %)			
Early neonatal deaths	6 (50.0 %)	6 (50.0 %)			

Note: IUFD = Intrauterine fetal death; OR = Odds ratio; CI = Confidence interval. $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Table 2: Apgar score at five minutes by mode of delivery

Mode of delivery	Apgar ≤ 6 , n (%)	Apgar > 6, n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Assisted breech (n = 31)	10 (32.3)	21 (67.7)	8.68	0.013
Unassisted vaginal breech (n = 19)	—	—		
Emergency caesarean section (n = 102)	28 (27.5)	74 (72.5)		
Elective caesarean section (n = 55)	5 (9.1)	50 (90.9)		

Note: Apgar ≤ 6 at five minutes indicates moderate to severe birth asphyxia. No Apgar scores were recorded for unassisted vaginal breech deliveries because of stillbirths precluding assessment. CS = Caesarean section. $p < 0.05$ significant.

Table 3: Perinatal outcomes by mode of delivery

Outcome	Assisted breech (n = 31)	Unassisted vaginal breech (n = 19)	Emergency CS (n = 102)	Elective CS (n = 55)	χ^2	p-value
Stillbirth	6 (19.4)	18 (94.7)	7 (6.9)	0 (0.0)	7.09	0.029
Early neonatal death	1 (3.2)	0 (0.0)	7 (6.9)	2 (3.6)		
Live birth (survived)	24 (77.4)	1 (5.3)	88 (86.3)	53 (96.4)		

Note: CS = Caesarean section. Early neonatal death = death within 7 days. $p < 0.05$ significant.

Table 4: Fetal outcomes by birth-weight category

Outcome	< 2.5 kg (n = 66)	2.5–3.5 kg (n = 118)	≥ 3.6 kg (n = 24)	χ^2	p-value
Live on admission	35 (53.0)	114 (96.6)	19 (79.2)	51.80	0.001
Apgar ≤ 6 at 5 min	25 (58.1)	15 (34.9)	2 (4.7)	19.00	0.001
Perinatal outcome (dead)	17 (73.9)	6 (26.1)	0 (0.0)	21.77	0.001

Note: Low birth weight < 2.5 kg; normal 2.5–3.5 kg; macrosomia ≥ 3.6 kg. $p < 0.05$ significant.

Figure 1: Trendline showing the incidence of breech pregnancies over a five-year period

Figure 2: Perinatal mortality rate (PNMR) in relation to pregnancy booking status

Figure 3: Neonatal complications among breech deliveries

Figure 4: Clinical causes of perinatal mortality in singleton breech deliveries

DISCUSSION

This study examined the perinatal outcomes and predictors of mortality in singleton breech deliveries at a tertiary referral hospital in Southern Nigeria. The overall perinatal mortality rate (PNMR) of 301.4 per 1,000 births observed in this study is markedly higher than national estimates (39 per 1,000) reported in the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2018), underscoring the persisting burden of breech-related mortality in low-resource settings. The finding also compares unfavorably with rates reported in other institutional studies across Nigeria, such as Kahansim *et al.* (2016) and Isah *et al.* (2022), though it aligns with reports from similar tertiary centers in sub-Saharan Africa where access to skilled obstetric care remains uneven (Minani and Ross, 2023).

A key determinant of poor outcome in this study was maternal booking status. Unbooked women had significantly higher odds of intrauterine fetal death on admission and substantially greater perinatal mortality rates compared with booked mothers. This finding corroborates earlier reports from Nigerian and regional studies that associate lack of antenatal care with poor intrapartum outcomes (Shafaatu *et al.*, 2024; Onoh *et al.*, 2019). Booking during pregnancy enhances early detection of fetal malpresentation, facilitates timely intervention, and improves preparedness for operative delivery where indicated. Strengthening antenatal coverage and referral pathways therefore remains critical for improving outcomes among breech-presenting fetuses.

Low birth weight also demonstrated a strong association with perinatal mortality, consistent with the findings of Debero Mere *et al.* (2017) and Gantan and Wiedrich (2023). This relationship reflects the compounded risk of prematurity and asphyxia in low-birth-weight neonates. Similarly, low Apgar scores were linked to higher mortality, emphasizing the need for skilled neonatal resuscitation at delivery and improved intrapartum monitoring.

Mode of delivery influenced outcomes significantly. Elective caesarean section yielded the best survival rates, while unassisted vaginal breech deliveries had the poorest outcomes. This agrees with the Term Breech Trial (Hannah *et al.*, 2000), which demonstrated reduced perinatal risks with planned caesarean delivery for term breech presentations.

However, in many Nigerian centers, the decision between vaginal and caesarean delivery is often constrained by late presentation, cost, or lack of surgical facilities. Consequently, a context-specific approach is needed — one that prioritizes elective caesarean for eligible cases while ensuring skilled supervision and neonatal support where vaginal delivery is unavoidable.

The pattern of causes of perinatal death in this study mirrors findings elsewhere, with **birth asphyxia** remaining the leading cause. High rates of asphyxia among unbooked patients may reflect delays in presentation, intrapartum fetal distress, or absence of skilled attendants. Continuous training in breech delivery techniques, effective fetal monitoring, and prompt neonatal resuscitation are therefore essential components of perinatal survival strategies in resource-limited settings.

The findings underscore the need for routine antenatal ultrasound screening to identify breech presentation early, effective birth preparedness counseling, and referral to facilities with surgical capacity. Policy interventions that subsidize caesarean section costs and improve emergency obstetric care could further reduce preventable perinatal deaths. Strengthening institutional delivery systems, equipping secondary centers, and continuous training of birth attendants are also critical to improving outcomes.

Limitations

This study was limited by its retrospective design, which depended on the accuracy and completeness of hospital records. Missing data and inability to include all relevant covariates precluded the use of multivariate regression, limiting adjustment for confounders. The study's single-center design also constrains generalizability to other settings. Nevertheless, the findings provide valuable insights into modifiable risk factors for perinatal mortality in breech deliveries within similar low-resource contexts.

Conclusion

Breech presentation continues to contribute substantially to perinatal mortality in Nigeria, with unbooked status, low birth weight, and mode of delivery emerging as major predictors of poor

outcome. Early identification of breech presentation, improved antenatal coverage, and access to timely, skilled obstetric and neonatal care remain central to reducing the burden of breech-related perinatal deaths.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Momoh conceptualized the study. All authors participated in the execution of the study. Eigbedion and Doherty provided clinical guidance and oversight from a paediatric perspective. Data analysis was performed by Yaya, Isenalumhe, and Afekhobe. Ogbiti drafted the initial manuscript, while Ojeh critically reviewed and revised the final version. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

